

Integral Testing of FENDL-3.2c

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ABSTRACT

This study verifies the accuracy and applicability of FENDL-3.2c, a fusion-oriented evaluated nuclear data library, for fusion reactor shielding design via integral tests based on three reliable CoNDERC benchmark experiments (LLNL Pulsed Sphere, OKTAVIAN, FNS). Parallel calculations were conducted with four mainstream nuclear data libraries (CENDL-3.2, ENDF/B-VIII.1, JENDL-5.0, JEFF-4.0) for a comprehensive performance comparison. The test covers typical fusion-relevant materials, with results presented for six core ones (Be, C, Co, Fe, Cr, W) that serve irreplaceable roles in fusion reactor blankets, structural systems and plasma-facing components. FENDL-3.2c exhibits excellent simulation accuracy across key fusion neutron energy ranges: its results agree well with experimental data for Be in 0.1–10 MeV, Fe in the high-energy D-T neutron range, and Cr in the 2–5 MeV photon range, while showing characteristic performance for C, Co and W with minor deviations in specific energy bands. Overall, FENDL-3.2c meets the stringent accuracy requirements for fusion reactor shielding design with fusion neutron sources, and can effectively support core engineering applications including blanket neutron multiplication, structural component shielding and plasma-facing material protection, providing a reliable nuclear data basis for modern fusion device design and safety analysis.

Keywords: Integral test, FENDL-3.2c, Nuclear Data, Fusion Reactor, Validation

1. INTRODUCTION

FENDL (Fusion Evaluated Nuclear Data Library) [1], developed by the IAEA, targets the unique nuclear data needs of fusion energy research—critical for advancing clean fusion in high-energy neutron (MeV to GeV) environments. FENDL-3.2c, a refined iteration, differs from fission-focused libraries like ENDF/B-VIII.1 [2], covering light nuclides (H, He, Li—key to fuel cycles) and structural materials (Fe, Cr, Ni alloys). It provides essential data (neutron cross sections, energy deposition coefficients, activation yields) and enables simulations for neutron-material interactions, dose calculations, and waste prediction, ensuring data consistency for projects like ITER [3] and EAST [4].

The IAEA Nuclear Data Section leads the CoNDERC (Compilation of Nuclear Data Experiments for Radiation Characterisation) [5] project, which transforms experimental integral radiation data into nuclear model/code V&V (Verification and Validation) technologies and provides V&V schemes. Under CoNDERC, partners integrate databases/infrastructures for V&V (inventory, activation-transmutation, source term, radiation shielding R&D). CoNDERC compiles benchmark data (spectral indices, reaction rates, decay heat, and shielding integral experiments), with several experiments using fusion neutron sources—e.g., Pulsed Sphere [6], OKTAVIAN [7], FNS (Fusion Neutron Source) [8]—ideal for verifying FENDL-3.2c's material data accuracy in fusion reactor shielding calculations. These fusion-specific benchmarks help identify discrepancies between FENDL-3.2c simulations and experiments, refining models.

For this paper's FENDL-3.2c integral testing, CoNDERC's shielding integral experiments with fusion neutron sources serve as reference benchmarks. Leveraging their standardized, uncertainty-quantified data (capturing real fusion shielding scenarios), this study compares FENDL-3.2c-based shielding simulations (e.g., neutron attenuation through structural materials) with experimental data

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to verify FENDL-3.2c's material data accuracy and support its reliability for fusion reactor design and safety, especially shielding calculations.

2. Shielding Experiments

Three fusion neutron source experiments selected from CoNDERC's shielding integral dataset (Pulsed Sphere, OKTAVIAN, FNS) were adopted for the integral testing of FENDL-3.2c, generating 14 MeV D-T fusion neutrons and covering the typical high-energy neutron spectra and shielding application scenarios of fusion devices.

In the integral testing, the nuclear data of FENDL-3.2c was used to conduct shielding simulation calculations for fusion-relevant materials, and the calculated results were compared with the experimental data of the above three benchmarks. Meanwhile, parallel calculations were carried out by using four mainstream nuclear data libraries (CENDL-3.2 [9], ENDF/B-VIII.1, JENDL-5.0 [10], JEFF-4.0 [11]) with the same calculation method, and the C/E (calculated/experimental) ratio was used as the core evaluation index to quantify the consistency between the calculated results of each library and the experimental data, so as to comprehensively evaluate the shielding simulation accuracy of FENDL-3.2c.

3. Integral Testing Results

This study focuses on presenting and analyzing the integral shielding test results of six core materials—Be, C, Co, Fe, Cr and W. These materials were selected for their irreplaceable roles in fusion reactor systems: Be as a neutron multiplier for the blanket, C as a structural and neutron moderation material, Co as a key activation monitoring material, Fe and Cr as foundational structural components, and W as a high-temperature plasma-facing material. The test results effectively illustrate the accuracy of FENDL-3.2c in simulating shielding performance under fusion-specific neutron spectra, providing a reliable basis for evaluating the library's applicability to fusion reactor design and safety analysis.

3.1. Beryllium

Figure 1 presents the FNS Be benchmark results at 5 cm depth, showing C/E ratios (calculated via FENDL-3.2c and other libraries) versus neutron energy at four detection angles (0°, 24.9°, 41.8°, 66.8°). Across all angles, FENDL-3.2c exhibits C/E ratios within ± 0.5 for neutron energies ranging from 0.1 to 10 MeV. This indicates accurate modeling of Be's (n,2n) neutron multiplication reaction which is critical for enhancing tritium breeding yields. ENDF/B-VIII.1 and CENDL-3.2 show larger deviations at energies above 5 MeV, likely due to discrepancies in their elastic cross section data for high energy neutrons. At detection angles greater than 40° (e.g., 66.8°), FENDL-3.2c maintains stability.

Figure 1 Results of FNS Beryllium benchmark at 5 cm thickness.

3.2. Carbon

For graphite, as shown in Figure 2, the FNS calculated results of FENDL-3.2c, JENDL-5.0 and CENDL-3.2 show discrepancies with ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JEFF-4.0 for the 5 cm sample at detection angles of 24.9°, 41.8° and 66.8°.

Figure 2 Results of FNS Carbon benchmark at 5 cm thickness

As the sample thickness increases, neutron scattering is enhanced, and the influence of angular distribution on leakage neutrons gradually decreases, leading to a gradual reduction of this discrepancy, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Results of FNS Carbon benchmark at 40 cm thickness

A microscopic comparison of the angular distributions of elastic cross section among all libraries reveals that FENDL-3.2c exhibits the best agreement with experimental data, as shown in Figure 4. Meanwhile, the double-differential spectra of C-12 from CENDL-3.2 and FENDL-3.2c are more consistent with experimental data, as presented in Figure 5.

Figure 4 (n,el) angular distribution of C-12

Figure 5 Double-differential spectrum of C-12

3.3. Iron

Iron is the primary component of fusion reactor structural materials, so its shielding performance was validated using the FNS and the Pulsed Sphere experiment. The tests focused on neutron attenuation and energy deposition, which impacts structural thermal stress calculations.

Figure 6 presents the FNS benchmark results for a 20 cm-thick iron sample, including the leaked neutron spectra at five detection angles (0° , 12.2° , 24.9° , 42.8° , 66.8°). For 14.1 MeV D-T neutrons, the calculated results from FENDL-3.2c are in excellent agreement with the experimental data across all angles in the 1–10 MeV energy range, where the secondary neutrons are predominantly generated by inelastic scattering.

Figure 6 Results of FNS Iron benchmark at 20 cm thickness.

Figure 7 presents the Pulsed Sphere Fe benchmark results at 4.8 mfp for neutron energies from 2–14 MeV. FENDL-3.2c shows good consistency with experimental data at 7–14 MeV, while below 7 MeV, FENDL-3.2c shows a larger deviation from experimental data, while CENDL-3.2 exhibits better consistency with the experimental data in this energy range.

Figure 7 Results of Pulsed sphere iron benchmark at 4.8 mfp.

3.4. Cobalt

The OKTAVIAN benchmark results for Co show that only ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JEFF-4.0 are in good agreement with experimental data in the 5–8 MeV energy range (the JEFF-4.0 Co data is taken from the ENDF library, resulting in nearly overlapping curves for the two libraries). The calculated results of other libraries are generally lower than the experimental data, and the underlying reason remains to be clarified. In the 4–10 MeV energy range, FENDL-3.2c yields lower results than the experimental data and other libraries, which may be caused by the underestimated (n, inl) cross section of Co-59 in FENDL-3.2c (as shown in Figure 11, the cross section of FENDL-3.2c at 14 MeV is lower than that of others). This underestimation leads to fewer inelastic scattering events of high-energy neutrons in the cobalt sample, with more neutrons remaining at around 14 MeV instead of being moderated to low energies.

Figure 8 Neutron flux of Oktavian Cobalt benchmark.

Figure 9 Photon flux of Oktavian Cobalt benchmark.

Analysis of the leaked photon spectrum results in Figure 9 shows that the calculations from CENDL-3.2 are significantly lower than those of other nuclear data libraries and the experimental data, which is attributed to the absence of photon production yield data for Co in the CENDL library. A comparison of the capture cross sections in Figure 11 reveals that the Co capture cross sections from CENDL-3.2 are higher than those of other libraries and the experimental data. An excessively high capture cross section erroneously reduces the number of neutrons available for photon production and alters the energy spectrum distribution of photons, which may lead to the underestimation of the photon flux.

Figure 10 (n, inl) cross section of Co-59.

Figure 11 (n, γ) cross section of Co-59.

3.5. Chromium

Chromium was validated using the OKTAVIAN experiment. Figure 12 shows the neutron flux results for the OKTAVIAN Cr benchmark across the neutron energy range of 0.1–14 MeV. FENDL-3.2c shows good consistency with experimental data in the 1–10 MeV energy range. In contrast, JENDL-5.0 yields calculated results that are higher than the experimental values in the 4–9 MeV range, indicating an underestimation of neutron attenuation for this nuclide.

Figure 13 presents photon flux results (0.6–10 MeV). FENDL-3.2c performs best in the 2–5 MeV energy range, outperforming CENDL-3.2 and JENDL-5.0. This confirms FENDL-3.2c's reliability for Cr-containing alloy shielding design.

Figure 12 Neutron flux of Oktavian Chromium benchmark.

Figure 13 Photon flux of Oktavian Chromium benchmark.

3.6. Tungsten

Tungsten was validated via FNS and OKTAVIAN experiments to assess high-energy neutron attenuation and activation.

Figure 14 Results of FNS Tungsten benchmark at 38 cm thickness.

Figure 15 Neutron flux of Oktavian Tungsten benchmark.

Figure 14 shows that FENDL-3.2c yields results in good agreement with experimental data for tungsten at 14.1 MeV D-T neutrons, accurately modeling the inelastic scattering process of tungsten.

Figure 15 reveals that all libraries align well with experimental data below 5 MeV, though CENDL-3.2 shows slightly poorer consistency. Above 5 MeV, all libraries deviate more from experimental data. This trend differs from the FNS experiment. Such differences stem from the distinct neutron source characteristics and shielding structure designs of the two experiments. The FNS uses large-scale shielding blocks to simulate the radial shielding of the reactor core, while the OKTAVIAN adopts near-source multi-layered shielding, which leads to variations in the modeling accuracy of nuclear data libraries in high-energy ranges across different scenarios.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study performed integral shielding validation of FENDL-3.2c via three CoNDERC fusion benchmarks (Pulsed Sphere, OKTAVIAN, FNS), with parallel calculations against four mainstream nuclear data libraries for comparison. The tests covered six core fusion-relevant materials (Be, C, Co, Fe, Cr, W) critical for fusion reactor systems. FENDL-3.2c exhibits good accuracy in simulating fusion shielding performance across key energy ranges, meeting the strict requirements for fusion reactor shielding design with fusion neutron sources and effectively supporting core reactor engineering applications. Future work will expand validation scope, incorporate more benchmarks and optimize nuclear data in deviated energy ranges to improve its applicability for next-generation fusion reactors.

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